

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and
Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D4.6

**METICOS Common Information Data Exchange & Storage Model
(final version)**

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Terms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BCP	Border Control Point
CDME	Common Data Management Engine
DTVA	Data, Text & Visual Analytics
EC	European Commission
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDF	Hierarchical Data Format
NGSI	Next Generation Service Interface
SBCT	Smart Border Control Technologies
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

METICOS Common Data Management Engine (CDME) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way.

This document presents the results of the final iteration of CDME. This covers the technological decisions for implementing CDME and the installation of the products used for implementing it. It also described the work done from the previous version in order to support HDF generation based on the data collected by the platform.

This deliverable is based on *D4.4 METICOS System Architecture (first version)*, that describes the first version of the METICOS architecture, *D4.3 - METICOS Common Information Data Exchange & Storage Model (first version)*. It is also based on work from *WP7 Big Data Collection, Analysis & Requirements*, more specifically on task *T7.2 Development of Data Models*.

Deliverable D4.6 links the METICOS data model used to organize the various and heterogenic information captured by METICOS platform described in deliverable D7.5. Based on this model, it also discusses interoperability aspects of the METICOS components.

The deliverable presents the tools chosen to store and manage the model and offers some details about their installation. There is also a description of the products used to secure the access to model through authentication and authorisation.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

Common Information Data Management Engine (CDME) is the METICOS component that organizes the data captured by the system in a uniform manner, in order to be accessible to all the METICOS components. The data is organized in a hierarchical way, using a common vocabulary. CDME is fed with data from BCPs but also with the output from the METICOS components. The access to CDME is done through METICOS middleware. This deliverable presents the work done on this component.

Some aspects presented in DoA are no longer part of CDME due to change in the project scope. CDME won't manage financial information nor media information. Part of the media information that was planned to be stored in CDME was "credibility profiles for media sources". This implied some ethical concerns regarding the assessment of credibility. After the project scope changed, this is no longer an issue.

1.2 Document structure

Section 2 *Data model* describes the data model that is used to store the information gathered by the component. Section 3 *Data Interoperability* discusses how the METICOS components access and use the common data stored by CDME. Section 4 *Data storage* offers details about the technological components used to implement CDME and section 5 *Data access protocols and access* presents the components that enable the security of the component. Section 6 *HDF related development*, describes the developments related to HDF file generation and use. Section 7 *Conclusions* offers some conclusions.

2 Data model

2.1 Overview

METICOS data model aims to capture the data needed to assess the acceptance and efficiency of the Smart Border Control Technologies (SBCT) in a harmonized manner. The main entities identified include the type of technology, the subjective feedback deriving from the actors identified (i.e. travelers, border guards and policy makers) and operational data which are based on the FRONTEX recommendations and the available data captured in the Border Control Points in addition to the perceived influencing factors, as well as the various types of users of the technologies. Moreover, METICOS data model enables the harmonization of the assessment of the acceptance of SBCT in other settings, configurations and Border Control Points (BCPs) under the condition that the same data entities and their attributes are captured.

The development of METICOS Data Model has been the focus of the work conducted within WP7 and more specifically task T7.2. More specifically, the goal of this task is the design and development of data models for the effective representation of the heterogeneous data gathered for METICOS. In order to achieve the above objectives, we have followed a hybrid approach, both data-driven and knowledge-based. Regarding the data-driven approach, after creating a corpus of relevant literature, we employ Natural Language Processing techniques in order to capture terms and relationships between them which could be used in the construction of the METICOS data model. Then, experts' knowledge is harnessed to confirm the obtained results and build the data model entities, their attributes, metadata and the relationships amongst them, whilst enriching the terms with additional ones if needed. An example of this domain expert knowledge which was taken into account when developing this data model is the METICOS Technology Acceptance Model, which aims to model the factors having an impact on the acceptance of SBCT. The output of this hybrid approach is a data model, which leverages the domain expert knowledge as well as data-driven knowledge extraction and combines the complementary advantages of both approaches. It should be noted that the process of developing the METICOS Data Model is based on an agile approach and is conducted iteratively. More specifically, after having developed a first version of the data model, this was dispatched for feedback to the technical partners of METICOS. As soon as this input was gathered, the suggested changes and additions were integrated, and feedback was requested from technical experts of the field.

More information regarding the data model, the approach which was followed for its implementation as well as a detailed description regarding the entities and their respective attributes, metadata and relationships has already been presented in Deliverable D7.2 and its respective final version is presented as part of deliverable D7.5 (available on M30). This deliverable describes also the approaches used to mitigate the biases related to the use of NLP and expert knowledge in the development of the model.

2.2 A High-Level Schema of the Data Model

Below, the high-level concepts of METICOS Data Model are depicted. Please note that, each entity has additional attributes which are not shown in the schema.

Figure 1 - METICOS Data Model

The main entities depicted and captured by METICOS Data Model are:

- Actor (this can be Border Guard, Policy Maker or Traveler)
- Acceptance
- Technology
- Border Control Point
- Biometrics
- Operational data
- Subjective /Perceived User Feedback

Some of the respective attributes to the above entities are depicted in Figure 1. Please note that the rest of the attributes, metadata and relationships are described in detail in Deliverable 7.5.

3 Data Interoperability

All the exchanged information is translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all METICOS components use them. CDME is able to store information about the METICOS Ecosystem static information (such as actors – border guards, policy makers or travelers, procedures, equipment related to the project, installed sensors etc.) if it is available. It can also include the dynamic aspects related to the METICOS Ecosystem, including queue lengths, flight delays etc., if they are made available by the BPCs. CDME will mainly interact with the METICOS middleware, which will collect all the information from the METICOS Ecosystem, translate them to a common vocabulary and store them to the CDME. So, all METICOS components will be able to store their output data to the CDME through middleware. Furthermore, CDME is able to provide historical data and information related to the METICOS Ecosystem to all METICOS components.

CDME contains a model aiming to unify the representation of data originating from multiple heterogeneous sources and encoded in multiple diverse formats, in order to facilitate data storage and retrieval, as well as to support the interconnection and communication of diverse components of METICOS system. All the acquired information translated and presented in a form which is understandable by all METICOS components. Therefore, CDME relies on the entities, vocabulary, attributes and relationships defined by METICOS Data Model' in order to translate the heterogeneous data into a common language before storing them, which permits their interconnection and efficient communication.

The access to the model is realized through FIWARE Orion Context Broker [1]. This allows other components to query or update the model but also to subscribe for notifications about changes of the model.

Furthermore, CDME ensures that all the stakeholders, by being part of a peer-to-peer community, will have access to up-to-dated information. Each time a new update occurs, the knowledge will be distributed to the community, coupled with additional information such as the timestamp and responsible actions or persons for the update. In this way, the history of all actions will be preserved, adding another layer of security.

CDME will persist the changes to the model in HDF, creating an audit trail of modifications.

The data stored as HDF can also be used as a dissemination support of the project data since HDF is a portable format, with no vendor lock-in.

4 Data storage

The data model developed for METICOS is managed using FIWARE Orion Context Broker.

FIWARE is an open-source platform for building smart solutions that are centred around a model of the world. The model consists of a set of entities and associated attributes. The model is built by gathering data from different sources (IoT, IT systems, mobile apps etc.). Then the model is used for processing data, analysing and decision making. By using this approach, the details about the sources of information are hidden, the application use the relevant entity attributes. Access to the model is done through a standard API known as NGSI v2. The API is using REST services and JSON payloads in order to query and update the model and register for changes in the model. [2] [3]

FIWARE Orion Context Broker is a FIWARE component that implements FIWARE NGSI v2 API. It stores context information updated from applications. This information consists of entities and their attributes. It enables the management of context information in a decentralized and large-scale way. By using a context broker the platform can be labelled as “Powered by FIWARE”. [3] [1]

Orion Context Broker supports operations like:

- Query context information
- Update context information
- Subscribe to notifications of context information changes
- Register context provider applications

The broker is using MongoDB for storing the context entities. MongoDB is a document-oriented database. It uses JSON-like documents with option schemas. It supports field, range query and regular-expression searches. Fields in the documents stored in the DB can be indexed with primary and secondary indices. MongoDB supports replication in order to provide high availability. It is scalable through sharding, the data is distributed across multiple shards based on a shard key. [4]

FIWARE Orion Context Broker and MongoDB were deployed on a Kubernetes cluster. For deployment we used Helm package manager for Kubernetes.

MongoDB was deployed using bitnami/mongodb chart available at <https://bitnami.com/stack/mongodb/helm>

The chart installation was done with the following command:

```
$ helm install mongodb bitnami/mongodb
```

Orion Context Broker was deployed using fiware/orion chart from <https://fiware.github.io/helm-charts>. Orion was configured to use the previously deployed MongoDB instance.

The chart installation was done with the following commands:

```
$ helm repo add fiware https://fiware.github.io/helm-charts
```

```
$ export MONGODB_ROOT_PASSWORD=$(kubectl get secret --namespace default mongodb -o jsonpath="{.data.mongodb-root-password}" | base64 --decode)
```

```
$ helm install --set 'broker.db.hosts={mongodb}' --set broker.db.auth.user=root --set broker.db.auth.password=$MONGODB_ROOT_PASSWORD orion fiware/orion
```

In Figure 2 there is a representation of corresponding Kubernetes elements created after the deployment:

```
root@meticos:~$ kubectl get deployments
NAME                READY   UP-TO-DATE   AVAILABLE   AGE
mongodb             1/1     1             1           5d23h
orion                1/1     1             1           5d20h
root@meticos:~$ kubectl get pods
NAME                READY   STATUS    RESTARTS   AGE
mongodb-6ddbdf5764-kc9bh  1/1     Running   1 (4d8h ago)  5d23h
orion-6d954c5964-9mq2c   1/1     Running   1 (4d8h ago)  5d20h
root@meticos:~$ kubectl get services
NAME                TYPE        CLUSTER-IP      EXTERNAL-IP   PORT(S)          AGE
mongodb             ClusterIP   10.99.106.15    <none>        27017/TCP        5d23h
orion                ClusterIP   10.103.10.17    <none>        1026/TCP         5d20h
```

Figure 2 Kubernetes deployment of Orion Context Broker and MongoDB

For this version of the deliverable there were no resource limits configured for the 2 components. The resource limits will be identified as the project progresses, the model will be populated with data and we will be able to estimate the data volume. Also the resources allocated will depend on the number of API calls that we will be able to estimate after integration with other METICOS components.

Another component of the CDME storage model is HDF. HDF (Hierarchical Data Forma) represents a data model, library and file format for storing and managing data. It is created to be flexible, to support efficient I/O, handle large volume of data. HDF is portable and extensible. [5] HDF is currently at version 5.

As mentioned, HDF is not a component to be deployed. On top of it we developed a component that implements functionalities mentioned in section 3 *Data Interoperability*:

- storing entity vocabulary, attributes and relationship
- storing an audit trail of model modifications

These functionalities are described in Section 6 *HDF related development*.

5 Data access protocols and access

The authentication and authorization for CDME component will be implemented using the following FIWARE components:

- Keyrock – this component implements identity management in the FIWARE ecosystem. It allows the introduction of OAuth2-based authentication and authorisation security to services and applications. Keyrock supports the definition of users, organizations and applications. Keyrock can be configured both with a GUI interface and through an API. [6]
- Wilma – this component is used in conjunction with Keyrock in order to enforce access control to backend applications. Only certain users will be able to access CDME based on the permissions and policies to resources defined using Keyrock identity management. Wilma is a PEP Proxy (Policy Enforcement Point Proxy) that intercepts the requests to the protected application and verifies the access permissions with the identity management component (Keyrock). If the verification is successful, the request is forwarded to the destination application. [7]

In the context of the METICOS platform, these technologies will be used to allow access to CDME from the METICOS middleware. The middleware will mediate the requests to CDME from the other METICOS components.

The Keyrock component depends on a MySQL database for storing the defined the users, organizations, applications, permissions and roles. The 2 components were deployed as a Helm charts.

MySQL was deployed using `bitnami/mysql` chart available at <https://bitnami.com/stack/mysql/helm>.

The command used to install this chart is:

```
helm install mysql bitnami/mysql
```

Keyrock was deployed using the `fiware/keyrock` chart from <https://fiware.github.io/helm-charts>.

The commands used for deploying Keyrock are:

```
MYSQL_ROOT_PASSWORD=$(kubectl get secret --namespace default mysql -  
o jsonpath="{.data.mysql-root-password}" | base64 --decode)
```

```
helm install --set db.password=$MYSQL_ROOT_PASSWORD keyrock  
fiware/keyrock
```

For Wilma component we created a Helm chart based on the Docker image <https://hub.docker.com/r/fiware/pep-proxy/>

The chart skeleton was created with the command in folder `fiware-wilma`:

```
helm create fiware-wilma
```

After modifying it in order to integrate with the deployed Keyrock instance, Wilma was deployed using the command:

```
helm install wilma ./fiware-wilma/
```

The Kubernetes elements created after these deployments are represented in Figure 3:

```
████████@meticos:~$ kubectl get all
NAME                                READY   STATUS    RESTARTS   AGE
pod/keyrock-0                       1/1    Running   0           4d11h
pod/mysql-0                          1/1    Running   1 (4d11h ago) 4d11h
pod/wilma-fiware-wilma-64dfdf97d7-tmgww 1/1    Running   0           4d7h

NAME                                TYPE          CLUSTER-IP      EXTERNAL-IP   PORT(S)          AGE
service/keyrock                     ClusterIP     10.100.148.192  <none>        8080/TCP         4d11h
service/mysql                        ClusterIP     10.106.85.13    <none>        3306/TCP         4d11h
service/mysql-headless              ClusterIP     None            <none>        3306/TCP         4d11h
service/wilma-fiware-wilma          NodePort     10.106.49.223  <none>        1027:30507/TCP  4d8h

NAME                                READY   UP-TO-DATE   AVAILABLE   AGE
deployment.apps/wilma-fiware-wilma  1/1    1             1           4d8h

NAME                                DESIRED   CURRENT   READY   AGE
replicaset.apps/wilma-fiware-wilma-64dfdf97d7 1         1         1       4d7h

NAME                                READY   AGE
statefulset.apps/keyrock             1/1    4d11h
statefulset.apps/mysql               1/1    4d11h
```

Figure 3 Kubernetes elements for Keyrock & Wilma

6 HDF related development

Since the first version of this deliverable, work has been done in order to implement the persistence of data as HDF files. The result of this work is represented by 2 applications:

- Hdf backend – this is a java application that takes the data from Orion context broker and creates HDF files. It also contains services used by the Hdf UI web application
- Hdf UI – this is a web application used to present to the user the list of existing HDF files. It allows the user to download the files.

In Figure 1 there is a representation of these applications in the context of the CDME component and the relations with the rest of the METICOS system.

Figure 4 – CDME high level overview

Hdf Backend is able to query data from the databases in the METICOS middleware and update the data in in the Orion Context Broker. The data is queried periodically, it is converted using the data model discussed in 2 *Data model*

Each METICOS tool is able to send data directly to the Orion Context Broker using REST services. Each tool can also query data from the broker using REST services.

Hdf Backend is also responsible with the creation of HDF files. The files are created using the data in the context broker. The files are persisted on the file system.

The access of the users to the files is ensured by the Hdf UI tool. This implements the front-end of the CDME module as a web application. The user can download the HDF files using this component after authentication and authorization using the identity management of the METICOS Platform.

6.1 HDF Backend

The backend is a web application developed with Spring Boot framework.

The docker image is built using a custom dockerfile. The docker image is uploaded in the meticos registry (<https://registry-meticos.simavi.ro:5443/>) under the name `cdme/hdf-backend`.

It is deployed on the METICOS Kubernetes cluster with the commands:

```
@meticos_kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl apply -f meticos-hdf.yml
@meticos_kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl apply -f hdf-ingress.yml
```

These commands deploy the component on the cluster and creates the ingress for access from outside the cluster.

The objects that were created are presented below:

```
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get deployment | grep hdf-deployment
hdf-deployment          1/1      1          1          50d
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get pod | grep hdf-deployment
hdf-deployment-7569cd56fc-bnbtx  1/1      Running    0          50d
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get service | grep hdf-service
hdf-service             ClusterIP  10.152.183.36  <none>     8082/TCP    69d
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get ingress | grep hdf-ingress
hdf-ingress            public    cdme-backend.meticos.simavi.ro  127.0.0.1  80, 443    56d
```

6.2 HDF UI

HDF UI is the front end of CDME. It allows the users to download the HDF files created by the backend. It uses the services exposed by the back end for listing and retrieving the files.

The docker image is built using a custom dockerfile. The docker image is uploaded in the meticos registry (<https://registry-meticos.simavi.ro:5443/>) under the name `cdme/hdf-ui`.

It is deployed on the METICOS Kubernetes cluster with the commands:

```
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl apply -f meticos-hdf-ui.yml
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl apply -f hdf-ui-ingress.yml
```

These commands deploy the component on the cluster and creates the ingress for access from outside the cluster.

The objects that were created are presented below:

```
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get deployment | grep hdf-ui
hdf-ui-deployment      1/1      1          1          48d
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get pod | grep hdf-ui
hdf-ui-deployment-596b54dfb9-j2pkg  1/1      Running    0          48d
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get service | grep hdf-ui
hdf-ui-service         ClusterIP  10.152.183.30  <none>     80/TCP      48d
@meticos-kube-cp3:~/deployments/cdme$ kubectl get ingress | grep hdf-ui
hdf-ui-ingress        public    cdme-ui.meticos.simavi.ro  127.0.0.1  80, 443    48d
```

After the user authenticates, the UI lists the files that are prepared on the server. The user has the possibility to download the files as presented in Figure 5. In this case, the files that are available for download are the files corresponding to the traveller questionnaires that are available at url <https://pwa.meticos.simavi.ro>

<https://cdme-ui.meticos.simavi.ro/hdf-ui>

Centralization of answers for travellers questionnaires

#	Filename HDF	Download
1	H5Questionnaires16.h5	Download ↓
2	H5Questionnaires17.h5	Download ↓
3	H5Questionnaires18.h5	Download ↓

Figure 5 – HDF UI

Such a file can be used programmatically using a dedicated library for HDF. Or it can be opened with a viewer like HDF View available at <https://www.hdfgroup.org/downloads/hdfview/>. By opening a questionnaire file created by CDME, it's possible to view it's structure as presented in Figure 6:

Figure 6 – Structure of a Questionnaire HDF file

For each questionnaire, the file contains the list of questions, and for each question there is the content of the question (DS_Question) and the answer (DS_Response)
The content of a question can be seen in Figure 7:

Figure 7 – Structure of a question in questionnaire HDF file

7 Conclusions

Deliverable D4.6 presented the CDME component of the METICOS system. The component was developed in collaboration with other work packages (T7.2 for the definition of data model, WP6, WP7, WP8 for the development of METICOS components that query and update the data model).

By centralizing the data ingested and produced by the METICOS system and organizing it using a data model, CDME makes contributes also to the extensibility of the METICOS platform. New tools can be added to the system, and they can communicate with the existing tool using the common data model implemented in this component.

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